

Explanation of the Physical Pi using Planck's length

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Abstract

We have discovered that in high energy physics there is a physical pi that differs significantly from the mathematical pi. An attempt for an explanation is given here, which results from the quantization of the length, i.e. from the Planck's length.

Introduction

In mathematics it is known that pi is an irrational number, approximately 3.14159265. In physics, however, there are no irrational lengths. In addition to this, every length is quantized. The smallest possible length in physics is given by the Planck length. This number is 1.616255E-35 meter.

It is clear that for large circles the quantization of the length does not play such a big role.

But it is also clear that for circles with very small dimensions, the quantization of the length plays an important role.

In the case of circles in quarks and/or of circles in other elementary particles, such small dimensions are definitely reached in which the quantization of the length already plays an important role.

So it may well be that when it comes to particle physics pi no longer takes on the mathematical value in the field of particle physics, but that pi only has a few decimal places and that pi is a rational number (and no-longer is an irrational number) in the field of particle physics.

So it may well be that pi has the value 3.1416 in the area of elementary particles and high-energy physics. The explanation follows from what was described above.

In the literature Zhengxi Wang developed a table in the article "Pi is a Rational Number in Physics" in which the decimal places of pi are calculated depending on the diameter of a physical circle.

If you now continue Wang's table as given in this publication for small diameters, you come to the conclusion that with a diameter of $1\text{E}-29$ meters Pi only has 5 decimal places.

It is possible that the diameter of the circles which lie within particles and therefore for circles in high-energy physics (quarks, etc.) the diameter of these circles is on a scale close to $1\text{E}-29$ meters. As a result of these considerations shown above, pi would then have a numerical value of only 3.1416 due to the quantization of the length and the magnitude of Planck's length. Therefore this could also be an explanation for the physical pi in high energy physics being different from the mathematical pi.

References

[1] Zhengxi Wang, Pi is a Rational Number in Physics, viXra:2208.0105.